

Semantic storage of climate data on object stores

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Introduction

- New methods for storing large volumes of data, such as cloud systems and object storage present **opportunities**:
 - Improved access and user management over POSIX
 - Parallel reads / writes
 - Read / write from anywhere (no need to mount disks)
- and **challenges**:
 - Interface and access methods for users are changed
 - Exploit parallel and remote access nature of stores with S3 HTTP API
 - While maintaining a familiar and consistent API for the user
- S3-netCDF-python**:
 - Library to read/write netCDF 3 and netCDF 4 via a S3 HTTP API
 - Files can be streamed directly to memory or cached to disk
 - Files can be split into smaller objects
 - Multiple objects can be streamed in parallel

File and variable splitting

- NetCDF files are first split by **group**, then **variable**, then each variable is split into sub-domains. These sub-domains form the **sub-array** files.
- Access to the variable data involves reading and writing to the **sub-array** files.
- The size of the **sub-arrays** is optimised for two reading and writing use cases:
 - The user reads a single spatial point (grid-box) for all the timesteps
 - The user reads all the data (field) for a single timestep

N = number of operations needed to read entire timeseries / field
 n = number of elements in the dimension
 d = number of splits (divisions) in the dimension to form the sub-arrays

Object storage

- Objects** stored in a flat structure, organised into **buckets**, identified by a unique URL
- Accessed over a HTTP API, such as Amazon S3
- More amenable to remote access, cloud and multi-tenancy service models.
- Overcomes problems with finite POSIX users and groups by using access control lists per bucket or object
- Software defined system, easily extendable
- Custom *metadata* per object – searchable content moved from the file to the metadata in the filesystem

Slice writing / reading

- Client based architecture – number of parallel reads / writes limited to cores on client machine
- Read / write only the sub-arrays whose domain is within the slice
- Just in time reading / writing – access the subdomains as the user requests the slice
- Three stages (read)**:
 - Determine which sub-arrays are in the slice of the master-array
 - Fetch the sub-array data to either memory or a cached file
 - Copy the sub-array data from memory to a memory mapped array

CFA-netCDF conventions

- Splits a netCDF file into two components:
 - a **single master-array** file (kBs)
 - a **number of sub-array** files (MBs)
- Both are netCDF files with additional metadata encoded in a JSON string
- Partition matrix stores location of **sub-array** in **master-array**

Interaction of CFA component classes

An example partition matrix

- In S3-netCDF-python each partition is approximately equal – the dimension lengths for each sub-array are within 1 of the dimension lengths of the other sub-arrays

Streaming CFA-netCDF files to / from S3 object store

Why semantic?

- The master-array file contains all the metadata and domains for all the subarrays
 - Only need to read the master-array file to search the data
- Each subarray file contains all of its metadata and subdomain as well
 - Can reconstruct the master-array file if it is lost
- The variable splitter knows what each dimension represents (time, latitude, longitude, etc.) and acts accordingly

S3-netCDF software stack

Contact

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<https://github.com/cedadev/S3-netcdf-python>